

PREPRINT–Distributed Trust for Collaborative Network Management: Leveraging DLT in Multi-SDN Controller Environments

Javier José Díaz Rivera*, Ricard Vilalta*, Raul Muñoz*, Pol Alemany* and Lluís Gifre Renom*

*Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya - CERCA (CTTC-CERCA), Castelldefells, Spain 08860

Email: jjdiaz@cttc.es

Abstract—In complex network systems, multiple Software Defined Networking (SDN) controllers are often deployed across different domains to manage diverse underlay technologies. This multi-controller environment introduces significant challenges in ensuring security and trust, as traditional secure methods such as Public Key Infrastructures (PKI), which rely on Certificate Authorities (CAs), often struggle to provide the necessary flexibility, transparency, and protection against tampering. Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) present a compelling solution by enabling decentralized management and the immutable recording of network configurations. This paper proposes an approach where SDN controllers from various domains act as validator nodes within a DLT framework, utilizing Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT) as the consensus mechanism. This creates a distributed trust model that enhances collaborative network management by balancing trust among network controllers. By implementing a private, permissioned ledger, data integrity is enforced, and access is restricted to authorized stakeholders, thus maintaining consistency and trust among network configurations through a verifiable record of all transactions. The performance and operational efficiency of this DLT-based approach in multi-SDN controller environments are further evaluated. Experimental results demonstrate the practical benefits and viability of integrating DLT with SDN environments for collaborative network management.

Index Terms—BFT, DLT, Hyperledger Fabric, Multi-Domain Networks, Network Management

I. INTRODUCTION

The legacy telecommunication industry has traditionally relied on closed systems comprising integrated and patented software and hardware from a limited number of providers, creating vendor islands [1]. However, there has been a shift towards replacing these closed systems across various network segments—ranging from Radio Access Network (RAN), aggregation, and transport to the core—with open white boxes deployed on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware, effectively decoupling hardware and software [2]. Industry-led initiatives such as the O-RAN Alliance (ORAN) and the Telecom Infra Project (TIP) exemplify this trend [3]. Open telecommunications networks are expected to facilitate the creation and deployment of new services and operational solutions by welcoming new providers into the market at both hardware and software levels, resulting in a more robust supply chain and a competitive, cost-effective deployment of 6G networks, with reduced dependence on specific vendors.

However, the transition to open telecommunications networks introduces significant challenges regarding security and trust in this complex, multi-vendor environment [4]. Multi-domain networks, where multiple Software Defined Networking (SDN) controllers are deployed across different domains to manage diverse underlay technologies, present a unique set of issues. Ensuring security and trust in these environments is crucial, as traditional secure methods such as Public Key Infrastructures (PKI), which rely on Certificate Authorities (CAs), fail to provide the necessary flexibility, transparency, and protection against tampering. In inter-domain SDN scenarios, the need for rapid adaptation and dynamic configurations can render CA-based solutions less effective. This increasing complexity demands advanced, decentralized mechanisms to secure interactions and maintain trust among various stakeholders [5].

Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) offer a promising solution by enabling decentralized management and the immutable recording of network configurations. DLTs provide a secure framework for managing and sharing information across domains, ensuring data integrity and transparency [6]. In particular, DLTs can address the challenges of maintaining consistent, secure, and tamper-proof records in a multi-controller environment. The inherent properties of DLTs, such as immutability and decentralized consensus, make them ideal for scenarios requiring high levels of trust and security among numerous independent parties.

The consensus mechanism is a critical component within the DLT framework, ensuring that the network can reach consensus even in the presence of faulty or malicious nodes. Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT) consensus mechanisms are designed to handle Byzantine faults, which are the most challenging to manage in distributed systems [7]. These faults include scenarios where nodes may fail or act maliciously, sending conflicting information to different network parts. BFT ensures that consensus can be achieved reliably, maintaining the integrity and security of the network.

This paper proposes an approach where SDN controllers from various domains act as validator nodes within a DLT framework, utilizing BFT as the consensus mechanism. Treating each SDN controller as a validator establishes a distributed trust model that enhances collaborative network management. This approach balances trust among network controllers and

ensures that data integrity is enforced while restricting access to authorized stakeholders. By implementing a private, permissioned ledger, we can maintain consistency and trust among network components through a verifiable record of all transactions. The integration of DLT with network management operations is evaluated, focusing on performance and operational efficiency.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents related work with relevant studies concerning blockchain and network management. Section III describes the proposed system in detail. Section IV discusses the experimental setup and performance results. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent research has focused on the integration of DLT with SDN in multi-domain scenarios, which has the potential to enhance security, transparency, and trust. In [8], the authors present SAUSA, a blockchain-based authentication network designed to secure the access, usage, and storage of 3D point cloud data. The system leverages a hierarchical SDN-enabled service network combined with decentralized storage to enhance data processing and ensure quality-of-service (QoS) requirements. Communication within SAUSA occurs over multiple domains, each managed by an SDN controller. The framework integrates smart contracts to digitize access control policies, providing data owners full control over their 3D sensor data. The use of a hybrid on-chain and off-chain storage strategy improves robustness and availability while ensuring privacy preservation. However, the study considers Proof of Work (PoW) as their consensus approach, which introduces challenges such as latency and increased processing consumption.

The authors in [9] explore the application of blockchain technology to manage responsibility and accountability in disaggregated optical networks. The paper proposes leveraging blockchain to provide a reliable and trusted record of events and interactions among disaggregated network elements across multiple levels: among SDN controllers, between SDN controllers and underlying network nodes, and within disaggregated network nodes. By implementing blockchain, the study addresses the challenges of managing service level agreements (SLAs) and ensuring Quality of Transmission (QoT) in multi-vendor and multi-domain environments. The proposed solutions are validated in a disaggregated network testbed, showing good scalability and the ability to handle controversial service level degradation events. However, the study notes potential limitations, including the additional implementation costs and intensive processing resource requirements compared to non-cryptographic solutions. Furthermore, the study does not provide details about the type of blockchain or the consensus mechanism used, which are critical factors that could impact the overall performance and feasibility of the proposed approach.

In [10], the authors present an extensive overview of the integration of DLT and SDN, emphasizing their combined potential in addressing security, privacy, and scalability issues in

modern network environments. The survey highlights that current network scenarios often involve multiple SDN controllers managing different domains, creating complex multi-domain environments. The integration of DLT with SDN is proposed to enhance the security and reliability of such environments by providing a decentralized and immutable ledger for recording network transactions and configurations. The survey covers various uses of DLT, such as ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data transmitted across SDN domains. It also addresses the challenges of integrating DLT with SDN, such as latency issues, the need for optimized consensus mechanisms, and the overhead introduced by blockchain operations. The survey concludes that further research opportunities exist for real-world multi-domain SDN environments.

The authors in [11] discuss integrating DLT with SDN controllers for managing end-to-end (E2E) inter-domain transport network slices. They present two blockchain integration models: the full permissioned distributed ledger (PDL) and the complementary PDL. In the full PDL model, blockchain is central to all interactions among transport SDN controllers, storing and distributing all information, which enhances security and immutability but introduces latency issues due to transaction validation time. The complementary PDL model, however, uses blockchain selectively to store and distribute essential information, like topology exports and element traceability, while other communications use existing P2P protocols, mitigating latency. The study validates both models using a TeraFlowSDN-based testbed [12], highlighting their benefits and challenges. The authors emphasize adapting SDN controllers to support both models and recommend further research to optimize blockchain integration in multi-domain SDN environments. Our research builds on the complementary PDL model, addressing integration challenges with SDN controllers in multi-domain scenarios and aiming to optimize performance and reduce latency.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

SDN controllers collaborate in scenarios such as establishing end-to-end (E2E) connections over multiple domains, where coordinated management and orchestration of network resources are crucial to ensure seamless and efficient service delivery. The proposed system leverages DLT to aid these appropriate operations for multi-domain SDN controllers. This approach integrates SDN controllers as validator nodes within a blockchain network, facilitating a decentralized trust model across multiple network domains.

A. System Architecture

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the system consists of multiple network domains managed by their respective SDN controllers. Furthermore, the SDN controllers participate as validator nodes for handling the consensus of the blockchain network, while peer nodes are responsible for executing and endorsing transactions. This configuration ensures that the management interactions across the network are securely recorded and validated in a decentralized manner.

Fig. 1. System architecture of the proposed multi-domain SDN with blockchain integration

The proposed system employs a BFT consensus mechanism, where SDN controllers act as validator nodes. The BFT consensus ensures that during inter-domain communication, the veracity of the information recorded by each controller—such as device, link, or topology-related data—is evaluated based on trust in its validator node. The number of nodes n required for the BFT consensus is determined by (1).

$$n \geq 3f + 1 \quad (1)$$

In (1), f is the maximum number of faulty nodes the system can tolerate. This ensures that even if some nodes act maliciously or fail, the consensus can still be reached, and the information is reliably recorded in the blockchain. Consequently, tampered information from compromised validators is not included in the blockchain, as it would not receive enough votes to meet the consensus threshold.

B. Methodology for record evaluation

In the proposed system, logging SDN controller operations establishes a verifiable record of actions across the multi-domain environment, ensuring traceability. Trust is centered on interactions between controllers through their roles as validator nodes within the DLT framework. To ensure the veracity of the information recorded by each SDN controller, the system employs a methodology using smart contracts to handle operations for recording network management information in the blockchain. Each record is hashed to create a unique identifier, which is then stored in the blockchain.

The process begins by creating a hash for the entire record, ensuring a unique identifier for each piece of information. This hash is generated using cryptographic hash functions (SHA256), which provides a secure means of verifying data integrity. When an SDN controller needs to store a record, it uses a smart contract to handle this operation. To prevent duplication, the smart contract first checks whether a record with the same hash already exists. If the record is unique, the smart contract triggers an event signaling a successful transaction and stores the record in the blockchain. This event mechanism ensures that all SDN controllers know the information committed and the current records keys. The process is outlined in Algorithm 1.

In addition to recording information, the smart contracts facilitate updating, fetching, and deleting information. The process for these operations is similar in that they involve verification of existing records by their unique keys:

- *Updating records:* To update a record, the smart contract first verifies the existence of the record using its key k . If $SC.RecordExists(k)$, the smart contract replaces the old data R_{old} with the new data R_{new} and generates a new hash k_{new} for the updated record. The smart contract then marks the old record as outdated; $SC.PutState(k, \{R_{old}, status : "outdated"\})$ and the new record is stored with its new key k_{new} ; $SC.PutState(k_{new}, R_{new})$.
- *Fetching records:* Fetching records involves querying the blockchain using the unique key k . The smart contract

Algorithm 1 Veracity Evaluation for Network Management Information

Require: *Record R*, *ValidatorNodes V*, *AllNodes P*, *SmartContract SC*

Ensure: *Record R* is uniquely identified and securely stored
 1: $key \leftarrow createHashKey(R)$

▷ Step 1: Transaction Proposal

2: $exists \leftarrow SC.RecordExists(key)$

3: **if** *exists* **then**

4: **return** "Error: Record already exists"

5: $storedRecord \leftarrow \{RecordId : key\}$

6: $SC.SetEvent("StoreRecord", storedRecord)$

7: $SC.PutState(key, R)$

▷ Step 2: Cross-domain verification

8: $votes \leftarrow 0$

9: $vEndorsements \leftarrow \{\}$

10: **for each** *node* $\in V$ **do**

11: $verified \leftarrow node.vChaincode(key, R)$

12: **if** *verified* **then**

13: $votes \leftarrow votes + 1$

14: $vEndorsements \leftarrow vEndorsements \cup \{node\}$

▷ Step 3: Transaction Commit

15: **if** $votes \geq 2f + 1$ **then**

16: $consistent \leftarrow checkConsistency(vEndorsements)$

17: **if** *consistent* **then**

18: **for each** *node* $\in P$ **do**

19: $node.CommitState(key, R)$

20: **return** "Success: Record stored and verified"

21: **else**

22: **return** "Error: Inconsistent endorsements detected, record not stored"

23: **else**

24: **return** "Error: Consensus not reached, record not stored"

Note:

createHashKey() generates a SHA256 hash to use as a *key*

RecordExists() fetches a record by a *key*, and returns a *bool*

PutState() modifies the state of the ledger

vChaincode() executes chaincode and validates the result

checkConsistency() ensures all valid endorsements have consistent chaincode execution results

CommitState() commits the record to the ledger after consensus

retrieves the record *R* associated with the key $\rightarrow R = SC.GetState(k)$. The integrity of the data can be verified by comparing the key *k* with the hash of *R*, which should be identical.

- *Deleting records:* While data in the blockchain is immutable and cannot be erased, the smart contract can mark a record as deleted by creating a new block with the record status set to "deleted" $\rightarrow SC.PutState(k, \{R, status : "deleted"\})$. This approach ensures that the history of the record is preserved and the current status is accurately reflected in the ledger.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The experimental setup was configured as illustrated in Fig. 2. A Hyperledger Fabric (HLF) v2.5+ deployment was prepared to mimic a multi-domain SDN scenario using a BFT consensus mechanism.

The system consisted of an Ubuntu 22.04 machine hosting HLF components as Docker containers. Four orderer nodes, representing SDN controllers in different network domains, were distributed as separate Docker containers. Four peer nodes, configured to endorse transactions, formed the fabric for chaincode execution. The HLF components were deployed as Docker containers, with networking managed directly by a configured Docker network. Unlike other blockchain implementations such as Ethereum, where validators execute chaincode and participate in consensus simultaneously, in HLF, the orderer nodes handle the consensus process, and the peer nodes handle the chaincode validation and transaction endorsement.

The chaincode logic for the experimental scenario was coded in Golang, with functions for recording, updating, fetching, and deleting operations on network management data, including devices, links, and topologies. A single channel and four organizations were configured for the deployment, with each orderer node assigned to a different organization. Each organization also has one peer node to ensure equitable distribution and participation in the network. Consequently, the chaincode was installed and activated on all peer nodes, enabling them to endorse transactions.

To simulate SDN controller operations, JSON information of devices, links, and topologies was recorded in the blockchain as transactions. The data used for the experiments included various network configurations. Device data encompassed information about network devices, including identi-

Fig. 2. DLT experiments configuration.

fiers, types, and statuses. Link data detailed network links, including source, destination, and link properties. Topology data described the network topology information, encompassing device and link arrangements.

Performance tests were performed by executing each chaincode operation 1000 times for a given data set. The system’s performance metrics were measured, including transaction throughput, latency, and consensus efficiency.

Transaction throughput was measured in transactions per second (TPS), indicating the system’s capacity to handle concurrent operations. Latency was measured as the time taken to complete each transaction, from initiation to final commit in the blockchain. Consensus efficiency was evaluated by comparing transaction completion time with two consensus mechanisms, BFT and RAFT (default HLF configuration).

To ensure BFT compliance, an endorsement policy was applied to the peer nodes. This policy required that the chaincode execution be evaluated by a specific number of peer nodes to meet the BFT consensus requirements. For our setup with four nodes, BFT compliance required endorsement from at least $2f + 1$ nodes. In this case, with four nodes and $f = 1$, the policy required endorsements from three nodes.

Fig. 3 showcases the performance results as a histogram, which groups the chaincode operations into two categories: execution (including recording, updating, deleting and query (including fetching). The histogram presents the mean execution times and standard deviations for each category across three datasets: devices, links, and topologies. The results indicate that operations that write or change the state of the ledger generally have higher execution times compared to operations that query the blockchain, which are executed almost instantly. Despite variations in the dataset sizes, the execution times for each category remain relatively consistent.

Fig. 4 presents the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the execution times for each chaincode operation within the datasets for devices, links, and topologies. Operations that query the blockchain demonstrate very low execution times,

Fig. 4. CDF of the blockchain operations for all data types.

clustering near the origin of the x-axis, indicating consistently quick completion with minimal variability, which completes nearly all queries within 100 ms. Conversely, operations that modify the ledger state exhibit higher execution times, with a more gradual rise in the CDF curves. These execution operations, particularly for topologies, take longer, with most operations finishing within approximately 400 to 600 ms.

The impact of execution times was assessed through a throughput test, wherein 1000 recording operations were executed at various transaction per second (TPS) rates: 10 TPS, 50 TPS, 250 TPS, and 500 TPS. The actual throughput achieved by these operations was measured post-execution. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the execution times significantly influenced the actual TPS achieved. At lower TPS rates (10 and 50 TPS), the system efficiently maintained throughput close to the expected values, indicating minimal delays and effective operations handling. However, as the TPS rate increased to 250 and 500, the actual throughput deviated from the expected values, particularly pronounced at 500 TPS, where the system

Fig. 3. Execution time for each operation for all data types.

Fig. 5. Transaction throughput for recording operations.

Fig. 6. Comparison of BFT and RAFT consensus mechanisms.

struggled to manage the higher load, resulting in a notable decrease in actual throughput. The 'topology' dataset exhibited the most significant drop in performance under higher TPS, while the 'links' and 'devices' datasets showed more stability across different target rates. The payload size of the transaction has a direct effect on the TPS rate.

Fig. 6 presents the comparative analysis of BFT and RAFT, highlighting the performance differences across various transaction rates for the same operations and datasets. The consensus mechanisms were compared by switching the consensus mechanism on HLF while keeping the same node distribution. It was observed that while BFT is designed to provide high fault tolerance, it introduced slightly more latency compared to RAFT. In contrast, the RAFT mechanism demonstrated quicker consensus times. The trade-off between latency and fault tolerance is critical in selecting an appropriate consensus mechanism based on the application's specific requirements, which requires further study in real deployment scenarios.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an approach for collaborative network management in multi-domain SDN environments by integrating DLT with BFT consensus. By incorporating SDN controllers as validator nodes within an HLF framework, the proposed system establishes a decentralized trust mechanism for tamper-proof recording and sharing of network management information. This integration addresses the challenges of trust in open, multi-vendor network environments, providing a transparent and immutable method for managing complex network interactions.

Moreover, the comparison between BFT and RAFT consensus mechanisms highlights that while BFT is designed to offer higher fault tolerance, it incurs slightly higher latency. This trade-off between latency and fault tolerance is crucial in selecting the appropriate consensus mechanism based on specific application requirements. Future research should focus on optimizing the configuration parameters of HLF and exploring hybrid consensus models to enhance the system's scalability

and efficiency further. Additionally, real-world deployment and testing in diverse network scenarios will be essential to validate the approach's effectiveness and adaptability, ensuring its robustness and reliability.

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